

Figure S1. Fluorescence decay profiles of CSB-5. a) Chloroform solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, monitored at 500 nm). b) Crystalline solid (monitored at 620 nm). c) Ground solid (monitored at 620 nm). d) Rubbed film after irradiation with 450 nm-LED light (32 mW cm^{-2}) for 10 min (monitored at 515 nm). λ_{ex} : 405 nm.

Figure S2. MALDI-TOF-MS spectrum of the material obtained by irradiation of a rubbed film of CSB-5 with 450 nm-LED light (32 mW cm^{-2}) for 10 min.

Figure S3. FT-IR spectra of a rubbed film of CSB-5 a) before and b) after irradiation with 450 nm-LED light (32 mW cm^{-2}) for 10 min.

